

VARIABILITY OF CAROTENOID CONTENT DURING STORAGE OF RASPBERRY FRUITS

Ortiqboyev Nurmuxammad Ulug'bek o'g'li

Scientific-Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Winemaking named after Academician M.Mirzaev, Researcher
nurartikbaev94@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-8522-6123>

Zuftarov Erkin Aybekovich

Scientific-Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Winemaking named after Academician M.Mirzaev, Scientific Secretary, PhD (Agricultural Sciences), Senior Researcher
erkin.zuftarov@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4755-5041>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18871786>

Abstract: This paper presents data on changes in the content of biologically active substances- β -carotene and lutein-in fruits of different raspberry cultivars before storage and during the storage period.

Keywords: Raspberry, cultivars Polka, Progress, Zyugana and Heritage, storage, biologically active substances, carotenoids, β -carotene, lutein.

Introduction. Raspberry (*Rubus idaeus* L.) belongs to the Rosaceae family and is cultivated as a perennial crop. Red raspberry fruits contain numerous phenolic compounds beneficial to human health [7].

Given the continuous growth of the world's population, improving food security and combating global hunger has become one of the key challenges of this century, including the development of new approaches to reducing food losses and waste [5].

Carotenoids are natural pigments synthesized by bacteria, algae, lichens, and almost all higher plants and fungi [8., 10]. Their biosynthesis is associated with hydrobionts, and these compounds are important determinants of plant and fruit coloration. Human requirements for carotenoids can be met only through food, dietary supplements, or medicinal products [1., 3].

Carotenoids are biologically active substances derived from isoprene and are traditionally divided into two subgroups: carotenes-hydrocarbon isoprene derivatives (ζ -carotene, neurosporene, lycopene, β -carotene, γ -carotene, δ -carotene, α -carotene, etc.) and xanthophylls-oxygenated derivatives of carotenes (lutein, zeaxanthin, astaxanthin, etc.) [3., 6].

These important biologically active substances have broad pharmacological properties; their provitamin, antioxidant, radioprotective and anticancer effects are widely recognized. Collectively, these properties contribute positively to immune strengthening [3., 4].

Efficient extraction of carotenoids from natural raw materials (including fruits and vegetables), their analysis and standardization, as well as the development of medicinal and preventive products based on them, are feasible only when optimal qualitative and quantitative control is ensured [4]. In addition, carotenoids are natural plant pigments that impart characteristic yellow, yellow-orange and red colors. They belong to the isoprenoids group and consist of 40 carbon atoms. In general, carotenoids are divided into two types: carotenes (composed of carbon and hydrogen, e.g., β -carotene) and xanthophylls (contain oxygen, e.g., lutein and zeaxanthin) [6].

Raspberry fruits (*Rubus idaeus* L.) contain various biologically active compounds, including antioxidants, polyphenols and carotenoids. However, the carotenoid content in raspberries is lower than in some vegetables (e.g., carrot or pumpkin). The main carotenoids found in raspberry fruits are β -carotene, lutein and zeaxanthin. According to researchers, per 100 g of fruits the content is approximately β -carotene 8–30 $\mu\text{g/g}$, lutein about 140 $\mu\text{g/g}$, and zeaxanthin 160–180 $\mu\text{g/g}$ [11].

Today, modern analytical methods are available for studying berry constituents, enabling the determination of the structure and biosynthesis of biologically active compounds as well as their quantitative composition.

With this aim, we investigated the variability of carotenoid content in raspberry fruits during storage. The quantitative dynamics of the most common carotenoids- β -carotene and lutein-were studied in the cultivars Progress, Polka, Zyugana and Heritage.

Study site, material and methods. For each storage variant, raspberry fruit samples were brought to the laboratory, 50 g were selected, washed, dried for 15–20 minutes, and homogenized in a mortar;

- considering that β -carotene and lutein are soluble in organic solvents, 5 mL of 96% ethanol was added and the mixture was centrifuged for 10 minutes at 5000 rpm (see Fig. 1);
- the resulting homogenate was filtered using filter paper;
- since β -carotene and lutein were present in the extract as esters, saponification was applied to obtain free forms, using NaOH treatment;
- the prepared solution was kept for 2–3 hours in a refrigerator at 5–10°C;
- finally, 4 mL of the solution was transferred into spectrophotometer cuvettes, and carotenoid content was determined using a Shimadzu UV-1900i spectrophotometer following the guidelines of Delia B.Rodriguez-Amaya (2001).

Fig. 1. Extraction (dissolution) of β -carotene and lutein carotenoids from raspberry fruits in 96% ethanol.

In our study, spectral absorption was analyzed at wavelengths $\lambda_1 \approx 470$ nm, $\lambda_2 \approx 480$ nm and $\lambda_3 \approx 485$ nm (see Fig. 2), because β -carotene and lutein exhibit absorption in these ranges.

Results and discussion. Before storage, β -carotene content in raspberry fruits was: Polka 24.6 ± 0.40 $\mu\text{g/g}$; Zyugana 22.3 ± 0.25 $\mu\text{g/g}$; Progress 25.1 ± 0.44 $\mu\text{g/g}$; and Heritage 23.5 ± 0.36 $\mu\text{g/g}$. Lutein content by cultivars was 135.7 ± 0.55 , 136.6 ± 0.40 , 132.3 ± 0.46 and 130.8 ± 0.56 $\mu\text{g/g}$, respectively (Table 1).

After 5 days of storage in refrigerated facilities, β -carotene decreased to 22.8 ± 0.35 (Polka), 19.1 ± 0.32 (Zyugana), 20.6 ± 0.21 (Progress) and 17.0 ± 0.49 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (Heritage). Lutein changed to 132.2 ± 0.35 , 126.5 ± 0.25 , 130.8 ± 0.20 and 124.1 ± 0.49 $\mu\text{g/g}$, respectively.

Fig. 2. Determination of samples at wavelength $\lambda_1 \approx 470$ nm (1, 2), analysis results at $\lambda_2 \approx 480$ nm (3, 4) and $\lambda_3 \approx 485$ nm (4, 5), as well as overall analysis results (7, 8).

Similarly, after 10 days of storage, β -carotene decreased to 14.8 ± 0.21 – 18.5 ± 0.26 $\mu\text{g/g}$ across cultivars, while lutein varied within 117.4 ± 0.60 – 125.4 ± 0.40 $\mu\text{g/g}$. The lowest losses of biologically active substances were observed in Polka and Progress.

Table 1

Variability of β -carotene and lutein carotenoid content during storage of raspberry fruits at different periods

(Laboratory studies: Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Winemaking named after Academician M.Mirzaev; Plant Protection and Quarantine Laboratory, 2022-2024)

Storage period	Raspberry cultivars	β -carotene, $\mu\text{g/g}$	lutein, $\mu\text{g/g}$	β -carotene+lutein, $\mu\text{g/g}$	Ratio, β -carotene/lutein
Before storage	Polka	$24,6\pm 0,40$	$135,7\pm 0,55$	160,3	0,18
	Zyugana	$22,3\pm 0,25$	$136,6\pm 0,40$	158,9	0,16
	Progress	$25,1\pm 0,44$	$132,3\pm 0,46$	157,4	0,19
	Heritage	$23,5\pm 0,36$	$130,8\pm 0,56$	154,3	0,18
After 5 days	Polka	$22,8\pm 0,35$	$132,2\pm 0,35$	155,0	0,17
	Zyugana	$19,1\pm 0,32$	$126,5\pm 0,25$	145,6	0,15
	Progress	$20,6\pm 0,21$	$130,8\pm 0,20$	151,4	0,16
	Heritage	$17,0\pm 0,49$	$124,1\pm 0,49$	141,1	0,14
After 10 days	Polka	$18,5\pm 0,26$	$125,4\pm 0,40$	143,9	0,15
	Zyugana	$16,3\pm 0,38$	$120,3\pm 0,50$	136,6	0,14
	Progress	$17,6\pm 0,35$	$122,2\pm 0,45$	139,8	0,14
	Heritage	$14,8\pm 0,21$	$117,4\pm 0,60$	132,2	0,13
After 15 days	Polka	$15,1\pm 0,42$	$120,1\pm 0,60$	135,2	0,13
	Zyugana	$13,2\pm 0,35$	$116,0\pm 0,42$	129,2	0,11
	Progress	$14,4\pm 0,45$	$118,2\pm 0,26$	132,6	0,12
	Heritage	$12,9\pm 0,57$	$114,8\pm 0,85$	127,7	0,11
After 20 days	Polka	$14,6\pm 0,47$	$115,2\pm 0,56$	129,8	0,13
	Zyugana	$12,8\pm 0,51$	$112,0\pm 0,78$	124,8	0,11
	Progress	$13,9\pm 0,59$	$115,9\pm 0,46$	129,8	0,12
	Heritage	$12,0\pm 0,47$	$110,3\pm 0,71$	122,3	0,11
After 25 days	Polka	$12,3\pm 0,60$	$109,9\pm 0,57$	122,2	0,11
	Zyugana	$10,4\pm 0,45$	$105,1\pm 0,65$	115,5	0,10
	Progress	$12,8\pm 0,62$	$110,4\pm 0,45$	123,2	0,12
	Heritage	$9,7\pm 0,67$	$102,6\pm 0,32$	112,3	0,09
After 30 days	Polka	$10,3\pm 0,61$	$107,2\pm 0,55$	117,5	0,10
	Zyugana	$8,4\pm 0,35$	$101,7\pm 1,08$	110,1	0,08
	Progress	$10,8\pm 0,56$	$106,3\pm 1,17$	117,1	0,10
	Heritage	$7,6\pm 0,42$	$95,6\pm 1,58$	103,2	0,08

Similarly, after 10 days of storage, β -carotene decreased to 14.8 ± 0.21 – 18.5 ± 0.26 $\mu\text{g/g}$ across cultivars, while lutein varied within 117.4 ± 0.60 – 125.4 ± 0.40 $\mu\text{g/g}$. The lowest losses of biologically active substances were observed in Polka and Progress.

After 15 days of storage, β -carotene ranged from 12.9 ± 0.57 to 15.1 ± 0.42 $\mu\text{g/g}$; the highest β -carotene losses were recorded in Zyugana and Heritage. Lutein ranged from 114.8 ± 0.85 to 120.1 ± 0.60 $\mu\text{g/g}$, and in terms of biologically active substance losses Zyugana and Heritage ranked highest.

During storage for 20, 25 and 30 days, the content of biologically active substances decreased progressively. β -carotene values were: Polka 10.3 ± 0.61 – 14.6 ± 0.47 $\mu\text{g/g}$; Progress 8.4 ± 0.35 – 12.8 ± 0.51 $\mu\text{g/g}$; Zyugana 10.8 ± 0.56 – 13.9 ± 0.59 $\mu\text{g/g}$; and Heritage 7.6 ± 0.42 – 12.0 ± 0.47 $\mu\text{g/g}$. Lutein decreased to 107.2 ± 0.55 , 101.7 ± 1.08 , 106.3 ± 1.17 and 95.6 ± 1.58 $\mu\text{g/g}$, respectively.

Conclusions.

1. When raspberry fruits were stored in refrigerated facilities from day 5 to day 30, the smallest decreases in biologically active substances were observed in Polka (β -carotene down to 10.3 ± 0.61 $\mu\text{g/g}$; lutein down to 107.2 ± 0.55 $\mu\text{g/g}$) and Progress (β -carotene down to 10.8 ± 0.56 $\mu\text{g/g}$; lutein down to 106.3 ± 1.17 $\mu\text{g/g}$).

2. In Zyugana, biologically active substances decreased to β -carotene 8.4 ± 0.35 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and lutein 101.7 ± 1.08 $\mu\text{g/g}$; in Heritage, losses were somewhat higher, reaching β -carotene 7.6 ± 0.42 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and lutein 95.6 ± 1.58 $\mu\text{g/g}$.

References:

1. Зубарева И.М., Лжапустина Э.В. Влияние аминокислот на развитие гриба Блакеслеа триспора продуцента β -каротина // Вопр. химии и хим. технол. 2010. no. 6. pp. 37–41.
2. Марковскажа Э.Ф., Корзунина А.А., Шмакова Н.Жу. Пигментный аппарат высших растений приливно-отливной зон северных морей // Современные проблемы фиологии и биохимии водных организмов. Петрозаводск. 2010. pp. 110–111.
3. Печинский С.В., Курегжан А.Г. Структура и биологические функции каротиноидов // Вопросы биологической, медицинско-фармацевтической химии. 2013. no. 9. pp. 4–15.
4. Britton G., Liaaen-Jensen S., Pfander H. Carotenoids Handbook. Basel AG.: Springer, 2004. 646 p.
5. Corrado S., & Sala S. Food waste accounting along global and European food supply chains: State of the art and outlook // Waste Management. – England, 2018. – N79. – pp. 120-131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2018.07.032>
6. Delia B. Rodriguez-Amaya. A Guide To Carotenoid Analysis In Foods. ISBN 1-57881-072-8. Printed in the United States of America-2001. 71-pp.
7. Ilhami, G., Fevzi T, Ramazan C., Mine B., Ahmet C.G. & Ummugulsum E. Pomological Features, Nutritional Quality, Polyphenol Content Analysis, and Antioxidant Properties of Domesticated and 3 Wild Ecotype Forms of Raspberries (*Rubus idaeus* L.) // Journal of Food Science. – USA, 2011. – N76(4). – pp. 585-593.
8. Karnjanawipagul P., Nittayanuntawech W., Rojsanga P., Suntornsuk L. Analysis of β -carotene in carrot by spectrophotometry // Mahidol University Journal of pharmaceutical science. 2010. Vol. 37. no. 1–2. pp. 8–16.

9. Rosdina Rahiman, Mohd Alauddin Mohd Ali, Mohammad Syuhaimi Ab-Rahman Carotenoids concentration detection investigation: a review of current status and future trend // International Journal of bioscience, biochemistry and bioinformatics. 2013. Vol. 3. no. 5. pp. 446-472.
10. Xia Jianrong, Tian Qiran, Gao Kunshan Diurnal variation of photosynthesis in situ in the economically important macroalgae *Bangia fusco-purpurea* // Acta ecol. sin. 2010. no. 6. pp. 1524-1531.
11. <https://fdc.nal.usda.gov>

